

Orbital character and vibrational spectra study on carbon monoxide and nitrosyl compound $\text{Mn}(\text{NO})_3\text{CO}$

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Abstract : The geometry, electronic structure, energy and vibrational spectra of $\text{Mn}(\text{NO})_3\text{CO}$ have been studied using B3P86, B3LYP and B3PW91 methods at 6-31G basis set level. Three states have been found and all states have been fully investigated employing the molecular orbital theory and vibrational analysis. From the calculation, we have found that the singlet state is the most stable one.

Keywords : Molecular orbital, vibrational frequencies, nitrosyl.

Introduction

The interaction between transition-metals and carbon monoxide and nitrosyl is important in many areas. It has been almost 10 years since these complexes were last reviewed in the book *Metal Nitrosyls*¹. So, it seemed to us that an update of this rapidly expanding field would be appropriate at the present time². Carbon monoxide and nitrosyl are strong ligand and surface absorbates. Then can also be easily bounded to metalloporphyrins, heme proteins, and transition metal compounds of biological interest, resulting in a change of the biological functionality.

There have been extensive studies both experimental³⁻¹³ and theoretical¹⁴⁻²⁸ for small transition metal carbonyls and nitrosyls. Many important conclusions have been drawn for the interaction character between CO and small transition metal clusters such as mono- and bi-transition metal centered biological molecules. Recent work has also established that the characteristic chemistry of nitrosyl complexes is often markedly different from exhibited isoelectronic carbonyl analogues. We have studied the occupation of electrons and vibrational frequencies of $\text{Mn}(\text{NO})_3\text{CO}$.

Computation method :

We have investigated the three lowest-energy states with the molecular orbital theory and vibration mode analysis. The B3LYP²⁹ methods have been employed to study the molecule $\text{Mn}(\text{NO})_3\text{CO}$ in which CO and NO exist together. Therefore, a detailed investigation concerning the geometry and orbital character of $\text{Mn}(\text{NO})_3\text{CO}$ is very necessary.

The vibration mode of the molecule and the occupation of the orbital have been analyzed in this paper. If n is the number of atoms of a compound, the vibration modes of it are as follows : in nonlinear molecules there are $(3n - 6)$ normal vibration modes and for linear molecules there are $(3n - 5)$ modes. If a bond is prolonged and weakened, the frequencies are red-shifted; on the contrary, if the bond is shortened and strengthened, the frequencies are blue-shifted. The changes of the vibration frequencies and vibration modes must be relative to the transformation of the geometry³⁰. The popular hybrid density functional B3LYP method has been used throughout the study.

Results and discussion

The optimizations of the geometry have been performed

with the Gaussian98 programs by using B3P86, B3LYP and B3PW91 methods at 6-31G basis set level. Energetically, the B3P86 scheme works better. So, we report here these values only.

Mn has 5 electrons in the d orbital. With the effect of the ligands, the d orbital has been split into 2 parts, the e and t_2 . In the $\text{Mn}(\text{NO})_3\text{CO}$, there are three states ($^1\Sigma$, $^3\Sigma$ and $^5\Sigma$ states). The three states have different geometries and their electrons occupy different orbitals, and so does the energy. So we investigate the occupied orbitals in details. Then we use vibration mode analysis to study the frequencies.

The orbitals of Mn, CO and NO are $\text{KK } 3d^5 4s^2$, $\text{KK } 1\pi^4 5\delta^2$ and $\text{KK } 1\pi^4 5\delta^2 2\pi^1$, respectively. Because both the CO and NO are strong donor-acceptors and Mn could donate electrons, they can form compounds. In this compound, Mn has an empty d orbital and the CO has an empty 2π orbital, while the NO has alone occupied the 2π orbital. Because of the energy of the orbital, the $3d^5$ can be combined with the $2\pi^1$ of the NO, and the $5\delta^2$ can be combined with the $4s^2$. As there is too large energy gap (see Table 1) between the two orbitals, they do not mix with each other much. But they can influence each other indeed. Because of the effect, they are in different occupied orbital (see Table 2), they have different geometries as well (see Fig. 1).

Table 1. Optimized geometric parameters (Å) and energy (kcal/mol) at three theoretical levels with a 6-31G basis set for $\text{Mn}(\text{NO})_3\text{CO}$ at the three states

Species	Singlet	Triplet	Quintet
Energy	-1655.87	-1655.40	-1655.36
$R_{\text{Mn-C}}$	1.85	1.83	1.79
$R_{\text{Mn-N1}}$	1.67	1.75	1.76
$R_{\text{Mn-N2}}$	1.67	1.74	1.78
$R_{\text{Mn-N3}}$	1.67	1.74	1.78
$\angle\text{CMnN1}$	106.15	98.09	96.00
$\angle\text{CMnN2}$	112.57	98.08	98.80
$\angle\text{CMnN3}$	112.57	98.06	98.82
$\angle\text{MnNO1}$	174.17	178.35	160.29
$\angle\text{MnNO2}$	174.19	178.27	145.56
$\angle\text{MnNO3}$	174.16	178.32	145.44
$\angle\text{N1MnN3}$	112.60	118.09	111.40
$\angle\text{N2MnN1}$	112.57	118.01	131.34
$\angle\text{N3MnN}$	112.57	118.08	111.34

Table 2. The detailed energy of the electrons in different MO at different states (eV)

Spin	Alpha	Beta
	-0.311 ^a (-0.327) ^b	-0.311 ^a (-0.355) ^b
38	(-0.336) ^c	(-0.328) ^c
	-0.311	-0.311
39	(-0.327)	(-0.355)
	(-0.327)	(-0.322)
	-0.270	-0.270
40	(-0.309)	(-0.304)
	(-0.324)	(-0.307)
	-0.270	
41	(-0.309)	-0.270
	(-0.310)	(-0.304)
	-0.260	
42	(-0.284)	-0.260
	(-0.290)	
	(-0.243) ^b	
43	(-0.268) ^c	
44	(-0.256) ^c	

^aData at the singlet state, ^bdata at the triplet state, ^cdata at the quintet state.

The singlet state ($^1\Sigma$) :

Since all the ligands have strong forces field, Mn is low-spin. The HOMO of the $\text{Mn}(\text{NO})_3\text{CO}$ is formed by Mn $3d^5 4s^2$, three NO $2\pi^1$ and CO $5\delta^2$. Because the orbitals of Mn ($3d^5$) and the NO ($2\pi^1$) are near in energy, they can integrate and form the new MO, while the $4s^2$ orbital of Mn and $5\delta^2$ of CO integrate and form the other new MO. Mn has 4 electrons geminated before the MO is formed, so they are identical in energy and the energy is -0.311 eV (see Table 1). The 4 electrons occupy orbital e . There is an electron alone, and the electron occupies the new MO with 3 NO $2\pi^1$. The 4 electrons are in 2 orbitals, as they are in the same MO t_2 : their energy is -0.270 eV. The $4s^2$ orbital of Mn and $5\delta^2$ of CO form the new MO occupied by 4 electrons.

The geometry (see Table 2) of the molecule is tetrahedral. The Mn lies in the center of the tetrahedron, and the 4 ligands stand on the 4 cross culminations. Inspecting the molecular geometry, we reveal that the d_{z^2} and $d_{x^2-y^2}$ orbitals of Mn form the e . The d_{z^2} and $d_{x^2-y^2}$ do not confront the ligand, and so the energy of the orbital is lower than that of the t_2 . The 4 electrons which occupy the 2 orbitals have geminated in Mn before the MO is formed. Meanwhile, the d_{xy} , d_{yz} and d_{zx} of Mn belong to

Fig. 1. The optimized geometry of the three states.

t_2 . They can combine with $2\pi^1$ orbital of NO and form the new MO, and the 4 electrons geminate and occupy 2 of them. Because the energy of the $5d^2$ orbital of CO is near to the $4s^2$ orbital of Mn they can form the new MO. The energy of the d orbital is lowered because of the existence of the abrupt energy. So the energy of the new MO is -0.260 eV.

The geometry, which was estimated by B3LYP at the 6-31G basis set, can be used to justify the results (see Table 1). The energy of the state is -1655.43 kcal/mol. We can use the state as a ground one, and then compare it with the other states. Since the singlet state has no lone electron, and the geometry is the nearest one to the normal tetrahedron (the Mn and 3 N), so the energy of the state is the lowest.

The triplet state ($^3\Sigma$):

The state has 2 lone electrons. This MO is formed by $3d^5 4s^2$ orbitals of Mn, three $2\pi^1$ orbitals of NO and $5d^2$ of CO. Although the orbital participates in the MO just the same, the mode of the orbital that electrons occupy is different from the singlet state. With the effect taken by the ligand, the 2 electrons in $4s^2$ orbital of Mn are compelled to $3d$ orbital, meanwhile, the d orbital was com-

bined with the three NO $2\pi^1$ orbitals of NO to form the new MO. And the new MO is split into 2 parts, e and t_2 . 4 $3d^5$ electrons of Mn occupy orbital e that has geminated before the new MO is formed. 6 electrons occupy orbital t_2 . One of them comes from $3d^5$ orbital of Mn, 3 of them come from $2\pi^1$ orbital of NO and the other 2 are $4s^2$ orbitals of Mn. The new MO is formed by $3d$ orbital of Mn, $2\pi^1$ of NO and 2 of the electrons come from $4s$ orbital. The new MO contains a large part of $2\pi^1$ of NO. It means that a part of the electrons come from $4s$ orbital feed back to the ligand orbital. This modality reduces the accumulation of the electronic charge in Mn. As a result, the $4s$ electrons of Mn transfer to $3d$ orbital, the $5d^2$ orbital of CO occupies the new MO that is composed of the $4s$ orbital of Mn and $5d^2$ orbital of CO. As there are only 2 electrons in the MO, in order to achieve the lowest repulsion, the spins of the 2 electrons are same. So the two electrons occupy 2 orbitals. The 2 $4s$ electrons of Mn transfer to $3d$ orbital, which makes the repulsion energy higher, so the energy of this state is higher than the singlet one.

In the new MO, $3d$ orbital is still split into 2 parts, e and t_2 . The d_{xy} , d_{yz} and d_{zx} belong to t_2 , while the d_{z^2}

and $d_{x^2-y^2}$ belong to e . With the effect taken by the ligand, the orbital is distorted. Even the $4s^2$ electrons in Mn transfer to $3d$ orbital of Mn. We know that the energy of this state is higher than the singlet state and the energy of the triplet i.e. -1655.40 kcal/mol. The point that is worthy to note is the energy difference of spin alpha and beta in the new MO. But in the singlet state, the energy is equal. That is due to two alone electrons in the state, and they have the same spin alpha, the repulsion of the electrons makes the energy lower than the singlet one in the same orbital energy level. But the energy of the whole molecule is higher than the singlet one.

The geometry of the molecule is a distorted tetrahedron (see Table 1). The energy of the whole molecule is higher than that in the singlet state. From the geometry, we have know that the singlet one is more symmetric than the triplet one. So the energy of the singlet is lower than the triplet.

The quintet ($^5\Sigma$) :

In this state, the atom Mn is nearer to the NNN plane, and the geometry makes the d orbital distorted. The t_2 which is composed by d_{xy} , d_{yz} and d_{zx} is high and it is nearer to the new MO upstairs which is composed by $4s^2$ orbital of Mn and $5\delta^2$ of CO orbital. The orbital composed by $4s^2$ of Mn and $5\delta^2$ of CO is occupied by 4 electrons. Two of those electrons come from $4s^2$ of Mn and the other two come from $5\delta^2$ of CO. Since the CO has empty 2π orbital, it can form a new MO that has 6 orbitals. When the electrons of same spin, the energy of the orbital is lower, so the 4 electrons occupy the 4 orbi-

tals. The 4 electrons are alone. Meanwhile, the $3d^5$ orbital of Mn combined with three $2\pi^1$ orbital of NO to form the new MO. The 8 electrons occupy the new MO, and all of them are geminated. Now, the d orbital is split into e and t_2 with the effect taken by the ligand, and the $4s^2$ orbital of Mn is nearer to t_2 , so it comes into the new MO more easily, therefore the energy of the 2 electrons is near to the new MO. Meanwhile, the 2 electrons that come from $5\delta^2$ orbital of CO occupy the orbital which is composed by the $4s^2$ orbital of Mn and $5\delta^2$ of CO and each of them occupies a orbital from where the 4 alone electrons come.

In the quintet state, Mn is nearer to the NNN plane, and the symmetry is the worst among the three states. The $4s^2$ electrons of Mn can not transfer to the $3d$ orbital because of the energy difference. As it has 4 lone electrons, so it has the highest energy among the 3 states. Now we will analyse the detailed geometry information. In the quintet state, the $\angle ONMn$ is within $145.44-160.290^\circ$, and we can see that it is not linear. And it has lost the symmetry, so its energy is higher. The $\angle OCMn$ is 179.42° , so the O-C-Mn is almost linear. The $\angle CMnN$ is within 98.80° . The bond length of Mn-N is within $1.76-1.78 \text{ \AA}$, so it is longer than those of the singlet and triplet states, and the energy of the bond is lower than those of the other states. So the state is not as stable as the other two. The energy of the molecule is -1655.362 kcal/mol. It is higher than the other two states.

In the three states, we find that both the triplet and

Table 3. The frequencies and frequency assignment of the three states (cm^{-1})

Species	The singlet state			The triplet state			The quintet state		
	Freq. (cm^{-1})	Freq. assignment		Freq. (cm^{-1})	Freq. assignment		Freq. (cm^{-1})	Freq. assignment	
Mn(NO ₃)CO	2043.28	CO	NO	2049.13	CO	NO	2028.65	CO	NO
		symmetric stretch			symmetric stretch			symmetric stretch	
	1844.79	CO	NO	1767.23	CO	NO	1700	CO	NO
		asymmetric stretch			asymmetric stretch			asymmetric stretch	
	1775.84	NO		1715.44	NO		1652.31	NO	
		asymmetric stretch			asymmetric stretch			asymmetric stretch	
	1775.50	NO		1715.28	NO		1626.87	NO	
		asymmetric stretch			asymmetric stretch			asymmetric stretch	

Table-3 (contd.)

732.84	bend out of plane		621.61	bend out of plane		619.95	bend out of plane	
732.51	bend out of plane		550.57	bend out of plane		591.05	bend out of plane	
590.48	except twist	CO	462.11	twist		522.16	twist	
724.15	twist		549.63	twist		534.74	twist	
568.61	twist		433.40	twist		458.73	twist	
568.48	twist		432.87	twist		434.12	twist	
464.18	symmetric stretch		427.76	Mn symmetric stretch	CN	375.76	symmetric stretch	
458.53	twist		301.13	except twist	CO	373.5	twist	
307.02	twist		297.50	except twist	CO	352.30	twist	
306.88	twist		261.82	Mn twist	CN	166.06	twist	
286.52	except twist	CO	83.33	NO twist		149.84	twist	
84.04	rock out of plane		83.15	NO rock out of plane		103.79	Mn rock out of plane	CN
83.92	rock out of plane		80.86	NO rock out of plane		81.483	Mn rock out of plane	CN
76.90	except rock out of plane	CO	43.24	rock out of plane		71.78	Mn rock out of plane	CN
74.64	rock out of plane		42.20	rock out of plane		46.48	NO rock out of plane	
74.35	rock out of plane		-48.02	rock out of plane		38.35	NO rock out of plane	
2077.60	twist							
CO	1856.29	twist						
NO								

quintet states are blue-shifted compared with the pure CO and NO (see Table 3). The frequencies of the triplet and quintet states are all lower than that of the singlet state, i.e. red-shifted. The bonds of the two states are prolonged and weakened.

From NO characteristic frequency we know that in the triplet state, the NO bond is still stronger than that in the quintet state. And, in the triplet state, the imaginary frequency appears. And so the triplet state is unstable. In the

quintet state, the bond is always longer than that in the singlet state, so it is less stable than the singlet state.

Conclusions :

The orbital properties and geometry for the singlet, triplet and quintet states of $\text{Mn}(\text{NO})_3\text{CO}$ have been studied in details using three DFT methods with the 6-31G basis set. The energy of the molecule is -1655.87 kcal/mol (the singlet state), -1655.40 kcal/mol (the triplet state) and -1655.36 kcal/mol (the quintet state). Con-

cerning the number of the lone electrons, the singlet state has none, and the triplet state has two, while the quintet state has four. The more lone electrons exist, the more energy they have and its stability is weakened. From the detailed geometry of the three states, we can say that the more symmetric the state is, the more stable it is. And the results indicate that the geometry which is the nearest to regular tetrahedron has the lowest energy.

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